

Identification of groundwater potential zone through the application of remote sensing and geographic information system

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ABSTRACT

Identification of groundwater potential zone by applying remote sensing and geographic information systems (GIS) for hydrological study, especially, the studies related to groundwater, is a emerging technology of modern developing world. The processes like Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and/or Analytical Network process (ANP) had shown its capabilities to help in delineation of groundwater potential zones in the respective study area. The primary step that has to be taken i.e., preparation of thematic maps of geology, geomorphology, soil, land use and land cover, slope, rainfall, temperature, groundwater level, drainage density, lineament density, etc. has to be done using toposheets or satellite imagery. The applications of groundwater modeling, geophysical method, geoelectrical method, visual MODFLOW along with previously mentioned methods has considered as most effective alternatives. Amongst all, weightage overlay method with the help of Pair-wise Comparison Matrix tends to be the appropriate approach to prepare feature layers with conclusive results. The integration of obtained weightages with image processing or mapping software indicates the best practice to get the result related to shifting of groundwater potential zones along with its detail classification.

1. Introduction

Groundwater is one of the most important parts of the hydrological cycle and is a precious natural resource which is responsible for the supply of water for agriculture, domestic, and industrial uses of our society. Consumption of water by human is largely depends on groundwater that supplies around half of total amount that consumed for drinking purpose in the world (WWAP, 2009) and almost 43 percent of total water directly used for irrigation (Siebert et al., 2010). Groundwater also plays a vital role for sustaining streams, lakes, wetlands, and ecosystems (Treidel et al., 2012).

Groundwater is an essential and dynamic natural resource. Limited knowledge of this essential resource, because of its hidden nature and its occurrence in complex formations at subsurface is still a big challenge for efficient management (Nagarajan and Singh, 2009).

Groundwater potential zone is the zone or area or part of an area, where the amount of stored groundwater beneath the surface is think as sound in respect to the surrounding area. It can be derived for a drainage basin and/or watershed of a river.

The importance of groundwater potential zone is broad for our society as domestic, agricultural and industrial activities are closely depends on it. As the groundwater is distributed naturally throughout the world and major part of world 's population largely dependent on groundwater for drinking water supplies, the usage and extraction from the potential zones of groundwater are increasing day by day; the rate further triggered due to rapid growth of population, high urbanization rate, industrial growth and utilization in agricultural sector. As a result, the rate of depletion of groundwater in the potential zones is rapid which ultimately causes water stress and degradation of this resource.

The study on groundwater resources, more specifically for assessing, monitoring and conserving the groundwater, the applications of remote-sensing has turned to a very handy tool with its availability of spatial, spectral, and temporal data that can be acquired from a comparatively huge and remote areas in lesser time (Jackson, 2002). Satellite images are very useful in study of groundwater exploration for its utilization in identification of groundwater potential zones with other ground features directly or indirectly. Satellite data can provide fast and useful basic information related to features like geology, lithology, structural controls, geomorphology, soils, landuse/land-cover, and lineaments that controls the occurrence and movement of groundwater (Das and Kader, 1996). However, it is quite rare that all the controlling parameters are studied together because of the insufficient data, integrating tools, and modeling techniques. Hence, the better identification and interpretation of prospective zones for an area can be done by a systematic study of previously mentioned ground features which is possible through detailed hydrogeological and geophysical investigations (Nag and Ghosh, 2012).

An integration of large number of multi-disciplinary data is required for decision making in groundwater studies and its development program which can be easily done in remote sensing and GIS platform. Jaiswal et al. (2003) has shown that, GIS techniques can be used to delineate groundwater prospective zones for rural development. Workability with both spatial and temporal data provides excellent opportunities for hydrogeologists to improve their understanding of hydrogeological system (Hoffmann and Sander, 2007).

Many researchers have used geophysical data with geospatial data, some other has integrated the lineament and hydrogeomorphology-based approach to study the groundwater potential zones (Nag, 2005). Saraf and Choudhary, 1998 have described the utilization of remote sensing and GIS in selection of artificial recharge sites. Several researchers (Gupta and Srivastava, 2010; Hutti and Nijagunappa, 2011; Manikandan et al., 2014; Nag and Ray, 2014; Nag and Ghosh, 2012; Nagarajan and Singh, 2009; Prasad et al., 2007) have used remote sensing and GIS for delineation and identification of groundwater potential zones.

Geomorphology and lineaments are the vital parameters in groundwater prospecting. A number of researchers like Kamal and Midorikawa (2004) and Singh et al. (2007) used satellite imagery in identification of geomorphic features and lineaments, through various techniques which are applicable in groundwater studies as well. Occurrence and movement of groundwater depends on many factors like geology, structure, drainage, physiography, etc. It basically suggests the requirement of a proper study by which delineation of groundwater resource using remote-sensing data can be done (Nag and Ghosh, 2012). Remote sensing and GIS techniques have become a very reliable and effective tool in delineation, assessment, monitoring and conservation of groundwater potential zone along with other groundwater resources (Mwega et al. 2013).

The present study has attempted to provide the information for identifying the changes that happened in groundwater potential zone using remote sensing and GIS.

2. Ground Water and Dependencies

The groundwater occurrence is a subsurface phenomenon and the identification and location of groundwater occurrence is depending on indirect analysis of certain features like geological structures, geomorphic features and their hydrologic characters which can be observed directly (Das et al., 1997).

According to a report of the Platte river EIS team, U.S. department of the interior bureau of reclamation fish and wildlife service on "Ground Water and River Flow Analyses" 2001, when groundwater moves slowly, river rises and ground water level rises are not simultaneous if the ground water level is responding to a change in the river. So, whenever the groundwater levels rise at the same time as the river rises, a third factor (e.g., precipitation) must be involved.

The global impact of landuse/land cover (LU/LC) change on the hydrological cycle may trigger the impact of recent climate change (Vorosmarty et al., 2004). There are several effects on atmospheric elements of hydrological cycle for LU/LC change (regional and global climate) are reported gradually (Bonan, 1997; Pielke et al., 1998; Pitman et al., 2004). But effects of LU/LC change on subsurface components of the hydrological cycle, more specifically groundwater and its related phenomena are needed to be explored.

Climate change has been identified as one of the most significant issues affecting the mankind now-a-days. According to IPCC, mean global surface temperature from 1861 till now have been increased by $0.6 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ and in next 100 year the temperature will rise from 2 to 4°C which will increase evaporation and evapotranspiration and this will directly affect the groundwater recharge, volume and surface groundwater interaction. Groundwater model is useful to predict the groundwater features and future impact of climate change (Singh and Kumar, 2008). By integrating the climate model and groundwater model for studying the climate change impact on regional aquifer can be done.

Rainfall is the major source of groundwater. In lower slope, infiltration due to rainfall is a factor of ground water recharge and in higher slope rainfall acts as surface runoff. Evaporation on the other hand acts as discharge factor of groundwater.

Groundwater can be expressed as the amount of water calculated by the resultant between maximum and minimum water table within an aquifer, which is totally dependent monsoon rainwater throughout the year. The aquifer recharge-withdrawal equilibrium can be distorted by exploitation or over withdrawal of groundwater resources which also creates a continuous decline in water table which will follow by much adverse surface and subsurface environmental effect (Garg, 1976).

The healthy vegetation and agricultural activity mainly occurs in ground water potential zones (Gaur et al., 2011). On the other hand, percolation of water to aquifer is low in areas of high vegetation cover the evapotranspiration rate is also high (Darwish et al., 2003). Vegetation type may also be act as an indicator for shallow, deep or sometimes saline aquifers e.g., phreatophytes indicates shallow, xerophytes

indicates deep and halophytes indicates the presence of saline groundwater in the aquifers (Jha and Pieffer, 2006).

3. Groundwater modelling

3.1. Utilization of GIS and remote sensing for groundwater modelling

The major challenges for data collection, analysis and management are the scale and the lack of infrastructure. This is the reason of choosing satellite imagery to acquire up-to-date data with good spatial and/or temporal resolution. The applications for mapping recharge and discharge areas were required to examine for describing the importance of such information for precise groundwater modeling. Along with that, the details of long-term fluctuations of the study area mainly in terms of surface area can be detected with the help of satellite imagery and GIS (Leblanc et al., 2003).

Lineament mapping using GIS and RS is one type of spatial modeling for identifying groundwater potential zone (Contes et al., 2008; Abdullahi, 2013). Importance of lineament for groundwater exploration in the central highlands of Eritrea was studied using digitally enhanced Landsat TM images to derive lineaments which were fractures of the earth surface (Solomon and Quiel, 2006).

Delineation of groundwater potential zone using remote sensing has done in upper Urmil river basin of central India. The IRS LISS-1 images and topographical maps can be used to identify hydro-geomorphology, lineament and lineament density map to prepare groundwater potential zone map (Jain, 1998).

The calibration of the groundwater model with remote sensing and GIS provide better understanding for the location and importance of recharge and discharge processes. This highlights the endorheism (the condition of a region in which little or none of the surface drainage reaches the sea) endorheism of the system with a significant part of the outflows being assured internally (Leblanc et al., 2003).

3.1.1. Spatial modeling for groundwater potential zone using remote sensing and GIS

Bhunia et al. (2012) have used Landsat-5 Thematic Mapper (TM) data to prepare various maps like seasonal land use/land cover and vegetation, hydrogeology, geomorphology, soil, drainage density, monsoon and post-monsoon water level and elevation, etc.

Sustainable management of groundwater is possible by integrating remote sensing and GIS. One of the best tools for the study of the controlled development of groundwater resources was hydrogeological mapping. On the basis of available field data and reports, the hydrogeological maps of the study area can be produced. The secondary maps can be produced by digitization of available data which includes topographic maps, landuse maps, geological maps and surface water maps along with all available layers of the hydrogeological map which may include hydrogeological units map, lithological map, surface water map, man-made features map, groundwater features, topographic map, base of aquifer map, isopiezometric map and isosalinity map (Elbeih, 2015).

Delineation of groundwater prospect zone and identification of land use changes can be done by integrating remote sensing and GIS techniques. Thematic layers, which may prepared by any GIS using ILWIS software, which are always were helpful for identifying the groundwater prospect zone along with the layers of geomorphology, lithology, drainage, texture, slope, lineament density etc. The layers can be ranked from 0 to 5 depending upon their influence on groundwater occurrence. Bayesian statistics is a useful method for converting the rank of each map into probability weight and multi-criteria analysis shall be used to find groundwater prospect zone. Studies indicating that, high groundwater potential area can be found along the rivers and its small pockets (Sikdar et al., 2004). On the basis of these methodologies with some modification, many researchers has completed their work On the basis of these methodologies with some modification, many studies has been conducted worldwide (Dar et al., 2010; Jaiswal et al., 2003; Magesh et al., 2012; Shahid et al., 2000).

Another study was conducted by Agarwal et al. (2013) where Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) techniques along with the integration of remote sensing and GIS has been applied for delineating groundwater potential zone in Unnao district, Uttar Pradesh. Three procedures has been applied there, which includes generation of thematic layers, calculation of AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) and ANP (Analytical Network Process) to find out the weights of thematic layers; and overlay analysis was applied to find out the groundwater potential zone. Three procedures has been applied that were, generation of thematic layers calculate AHP and ANP to find out the weights of thematic layers and overlay analysis was applied to find out the groundwater potential zone. By this process, the groundwater potential zone has been categorized into five different zones on the basis of their potential or capacity.

Groundwater mapping in hard rock zones can be operated by a spatial model based on fuzzy logic and GIS. Identification of the groundwater prospect zones can also be done using the fuzzy membership values of the thematic layers and divided all the prospect zones into different categories like 'excellent', 'very good', 'good', 'moderate', 'poor', and 'very poor'.

This method mainly deals with the prepared or derived thematic maps. If there is a requirement of incorporation of other factors or judgments, the method fails to allow that (Bhunia et al., 2012; Gumma and Pavelic, 2013; Sikdar et al., 2004).

3.1.2. Application of spatial modeling for identifying groundwater recharge and artificial recharge site

Identification of groundwater recharge zones and artificial recharge structures can be completed by integrating the remotely sensed data and GIS databases. Different thematic layers from primary and secondary sources like IRS 1C/1D geo-coded data and survey of India topographic sheets can be used to prepare thematic maps like Structural trend line, Lineament, Geomorphology and Land use/Land cover maps. Drainage, Slope and Tank maps may also be prepared from the survey of India topographic sheets. Besides that, Water level map and Depth to bed rock map were required to derive from the data collected from the public works department

reports. Along with that, preparation of the geology map of study area was required from the geological survey of India reports and finally, there is a requirement of carried out the limited field check for confirmation of details obtained from various sources (Ramireddy et al., 2015).

Identification of recharge and discharge zone of saline prone area can also be successfully done by using remote sensing and GIS. Break of slope, topographic dispersion, groundwater flow direction and vegetation was the indicator of discharge. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Standard Deviation for the Vegetation Index (SDVI) for low variability of vegetation, topographic weight index for topographic depression, and profile curvature for break of slope shall be used to run the process. For identification of recharge zone, the help of volcanic fracture and soil infiltration property could have been taken. For discharge zone identification SDVI is more useful for the study area. Infiltration property of surface feature is important for recharge zone identification. During the preparation of maps for recharge and discharge, uncertainties occurred due to temporal variation of climate and landuse (Tweed et al., 2006).

GIS and groundwater flow model may combinedly use to identify the groundwater recharge distribution and to simulate the behaviour of an aquifer. The study area can be divided in Basic Simulation Units (BSUs) which were homogeneous in respect to factors influencing groundwater process. Estimation of percolation and seepage losses can be done through the combined use of soil water balance model and a canal flow model. GIS can be used to derive spatial distribution of recharge and a finite element method can also be developed to check the validity of the model (Chowdhury et al., 2009).

For preparing the groundwater development plan for a highly degraded terrain and to estimate spatial and temporal variation in groundwater recharge, 'Thronthwaite-Mather' water balance method is one of the suitable methods that can be applied for each month.

Result of that method can easily show the recharge percentage of an area and amount or volume of recharge whether sufficient, more or less. Result of that method can easily show the percentages of the area, amount of recharge whether sufficient, more or less. For identification of artificial recharge and slide susceptible areas, the method of weighted overlay analysis can be applied which will show the favourability of artificial recharge of an area in terms of percentage. The methodology can also estimate the total annual groundwater recharge. As per the findings, if there is a presence of any forested part in the study area, that part did not need artificial recharge measure as the area will get enough rainfall and high surface recharge (Kannan and Mathew, 2008).

As the spatial modeling mainly deals with the prepared or derived thematic maps, it does not allow the incorporation of other factors or judgements with existing maps (Ramireddy et al., 2015). Besides that, for executing the process some parameters (i.e., NDVI, SDVI, etc.) and some model (such as canal flow model) may also require (Chowdhury et al., 2009; Tweed et al., 2006).

3.1.3. Geostatistical application in GIS for groundwater study

GIS and Geostatistics are such type of modern and well known technologies which can be cumulatively gives us useful results. Integration of GIS and Geostatistics for studying the groundwater has given useful information to researcher. Many researchers has used geostatistics as a tool of management and decision making for research in the field of groundwater research e.g., evaluation of groundwater quality (Lee and Song, 2007), capacity of groundwater storage and reservoir (Rakhmatullaev et al., 2010; Sharda et al., 2006), research on chemical contamination in groundwater (Cinnirella et al., 2005; Iskandar and Koike, 2010; Shamsudduha et al., 2009), groundwater level fluctuation research (Ahmadi and Sedghamiz, 2007; Cameron and Hunter, 2002; Gundogdu and Guney, 2007; Hu et al., 2005; Knotters and Bierkens, 2001; Theodossiou and Latinopoulos, 2006; Ta'any et al., 2009) and many more.

Geostatistics is a method of reporting spatial variability and estimation of the unknown continuously distributed variables. Rakhmatullaev et al. (2010) has found that the geostatistical approaches like trend analysis, arithmetic average, regression analysis and inverse distance method, etc. allows to enlarge the number of sampling points in un sampled zones, and variogram analyses for checking the structural relationship of data by providing easier and effective tools. Kriging is recorded as the most widely used and optimal method of interpolation. For normally distributed variables, kriging is the more suitable techniques to get the geostatistical results. Skewness can be described as asymmetric order in the distribution of the data. The distribution of values of sampled data are associated with large skewness (Basaran et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2009). Seriously skewed circulations can frequently be lightened by fitting the change of information. Natural logarithmic transform is the most widely recognized process for logging ordinary information (Wu et al., 2010).

Uyan and Cay (2013) made an examination at Central Anatolian district of Konya in Turkey between April 1999 and April 2008 for investigation of the spatial example and mapping of groundwater level determination that contrasts for the perception time frame and for assessment of changes in groundwater level contrasts with geostatistical strategies. Firstly, they have utilized a normal distribution curve to portray the middle, spread and state of the groundwater level contrasts with the assistance of Geostatistical Analysis tool in the ArcGIS software. Besides, they made utilization of Q-Q plot which was for the assurance of whether the conveyance of a variable matches the typical dispersion or not. Utilization of kriging technique in the examination for the estimation of the adjustments in the groundwater levels was likewise exceptionally valuable. GIS builds the extent of the spatial examination, and Geostatistics gives overlay and information control offices to help the elucidation of results. Geostatistical examination of information should be possible utilizing the ArcGIS software and the spatial dissemination components of groundwater level vacillations might just be contemplated.

The spatio-temporal variation in water table can be studied by using geostatistical technique in GIS environment (for e.g. ArcGIS). To begin with, the ground water statistical

data can be accumulated to prepare a data bank of the region. Diverse strategies that include Kriging, Inverse Distance Weight (IDW) to the energy of 1 to 5, Radial Basis Function technique and Cokriging strategy may presented for introduction of those obtained information. General Standard Deviation (GSD) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) can be introduced for getting best results in spatial zonation mapping of groundwater table by using ArcGIS. For temporal variation of groundwater table it is advisable to use different geostatistical model for different years. This method resembles the work of Ahmadian and Chavoshian (2012). They used this method successfully for the study of spatio-temporal variation in water table in Central region of Hamadan Province in Iran.

Machiwal et al. (2012) directed an examination for effective planning and management of the groundwater assets utilizing Geostatistics and GIS tools in a semi-arid hard-rock aquifer of Western India. The month to month information of groundwater levels of 50 locales has been gathered for three years' time frame (May 2006 to June 2009; barring 3 months) and broke down to discover spatial autocorrelation and fluctuations in the groundwater levels. As indicated by the investigation, the best-fit geostatistical demonstrate was root mean square error (RMSE) and connection coefficient (r) with kriging system for spatial mapping. Two spatial measurements (Geary's C and Moran's I) can be discovered which demonstrated a solid positive autocorrelation in the groundwater levels inside 3-km slack separation investigating that the spatial insights are imperative apparatuses for Geostatistical displaying, which help to pick fitting estimations of model parameters. But that, exponential model was turned as the best-fitted model among three geostatistical models, i.e., round, roundabout, and exponential model. From spatial conveyance maps the groundwater levels are emphatically influenced by surface geography and the nearness of surface water assemblages of their examination territory. The kriging procedure is useful for distinguishing basic areas over the investigation zone where water sparing and groundwater growth methods should be executed to secure draining groundwater assets.

The method is not applicable in every condition as a particular geostatistical model was suitable for a particular year (Ahmadian and Chavoshian, 2012). In case of a study, where we have to work with the data of several years, the application of this model is not feasible.

3.1.4. Lineament mapping for groundwater

Lineament mapping for identifying the groundwater potential zone can easily be completed through the use of spatial modeling (Contes et al., 2008; Abdullahi, 2013). Groundwater event being a subsurface marvel, the zones can be depicted in light of backhanded examination of some specifically recognizable territory components, for example, lineaments (Sener et al., 2005). A few scientists additionally found that LULC and water resource management are straight forwardly connected to each other; it is a vital trademark that influences forms like invasion, in this manner the procedure of lineament mapping assumes a critical part in distinguishing groundwater recharge sites (Mukherjee et al., 2007). A few specialists likewise found that LULC and water asset administration are specifically connected to each other; it is

an imperative trademark that influences forms like penetration, in this way assuming a pivotal part in recognizing groundwater recharge sites (Mukherjee et al., 2007).

Mapping of hydro-geomorphology, lineament and lineament density can be done through the preparation of groundwater potential zone map, which can be completed with the help of IRS LISS-1 images and topographical maps (Jain, 1998).

Lineament map can provide important information about subsurface fractures which can influence movement and storage of groundwater. Reports indicated that the lineament mapping and hydro-geomorphology is useful to demarcate groundwater potential zone of a study area. The groundwater study can be done using the indirect method of lineament mapping. Based on the tectonic origins and ages, lineaments can be divided into several sets; where conjugation of shear fractures may occur followed by the occurrence of higher and lower yields of wells, at the higher and lesser distance from the main fractures respectively. It can also be found that, the well yield of shear fracture is in the higher side in comparison with the previous one. Due to these, shear fracture zones can be found as more important than tensile fractures for the purpose of groundwater exploration (Solomon and Quiel, 2006). On the basis of tectonic origins and ages, a division of lineaments can be done into three major sets of geological structures. In Set 1, conjugation of shear fractures has been taken place. In Set 2 and Set 3 with shear fractures, high amount of well yields can be found away from the main lineaments and low well yields at a lower distance to lineaments. In the Set 1, high amount of well yields was founded at a lesser distances from the main fractures. This rate is much lower compared with well yields in the shear fracture. Studies explored that shear fractures zone were more important for groundwater exploration than tensile fractures (Solomon and Quiel, 2005).

By analysing data and field survey, it was found that groundwater always moves along the faults and fractures that were formed due to tectonic movements. Lineaments extracted from satellite images can identify two fracture zones which acts as groundwater storage and transmission zone. But lineament mapping alone is not always sufficient for groundwater investigation.

In hard rock region of Karnataka, for locating the groundwater potential zones a study has been conducted by applying the same method mentioned earlier. As only the surface features can be identified from geomorphological map lineament mapping was not sufficient for groundwater prospecting. For this, resistivity imaging can be used to identify the productive lineaments (Chandra et al., 2006). The efficiency of spatial modelling of lineament study for groundwater exploration can be increased through the integration of Remote Sensing and GIS technology. Importance of lineaments for identification of groundwater prospect zone can be processed using satellite imageries. Directional filters can be applied in the images which will identify the lineaments automatically. From boreholes lithology and field survey, lineament can be found as long rectilinear buried layer below thick layers of sand and gravel. Buried channels and layer sediments may act as suitable sites for increasing fresh water storage during rainy season. In

such cases directional filters can also be suitably used for lineament mapping for groundwater study.

Lineament mapping can be conducted by the interpretation of data collected using photographs taken through Stereoscopic LFC (Large Format Camera) and SIR-C L- and C- band SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar). Because of its high resolution LFC imagery can be found as most useful for mapping of fracture patterns and orientations. It can also be found that the shorter lineaments are important as they inter-connect the major faults.

Lineament mapping alone is not always sufficient for groundwater investigation. As the groundwater occurrence is a subsurface phenomenon, lineament mapping can be used as a method of indirect analysis for delineation of groundwater potential zone of some directly observable terrain (Sener et al., 2005). Along with that, it is dependent on LULC and water resource management in many cases (Mukherjee et al., 2007).

3.1.5. Application of geophysical method in GIS platform for spatial modelling

Integration of geophysical method with geospatial technology helps to study groundwater more accurately. Geospatial technology helps to identify the surface features which are suitable for groundwater availability. But it cannot provide sufficient knowledge about subsurface geological character. Only geophysical methods can estimate the subsurface character of aquifers properly. Integration of Vertical Electrical Sounding Resistivity (VESR) and GIS for identifying the groundwater prospect zone was found to be useful in Dhanbad district, Jharkhand. The VESR result showed that there is good amount of groundwater in soil covered and weathered zone where depth was around 5m and resistivity value was 50 ohm. Below this layer a zone of semi-weathered materials with 9m to 10m thickness and resistivity value of 214 ohm was found. In this zone, groundwater was found in non-interconnected fracture. Third layer was a good groundwater potential zone having value of resistivity 144 ohm. At last weightage overlay had been done for hydro-geomorphological map and groundwater prospect map (Srivastava et al., 2012).

Shahid et al. (2000) studied the hydrological condition of Midnapur district, West Bengal in which the integration of GIS and Remote Sensing data and Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) was made. VES was mainly used to prepare the geophysical thematic maps. Aquifer resistivity and its thickness were obtained from VES stored in GIS and then thematic map was prepared. Study also investigated that laterites can be found over the respective area. VES study indicates presence of shallow groundwater resources in the area. Weightage overlay analysis in GIS using aquifer and geological parameters show that 18.1% of the area was highly prospective, 39% moderately prospective, and the rest was poor for groundwater. To verify the model, the available pumping test data can be used which gave position relation with groundwater prospect zone.

In the study of groundwater, the implementation of geophysical method can be found as very useful. The geophysical data can be collected using Aeromagnetic (AM) and Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) process to apply in the geophysical model. For getting the proper result, the

method may also require the generation of DEM (using GIS) and detection of natural basalt caves for groundwater artificial recharge.

The geophysical data has been collected from Aeromagnetic (AM) and Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES), lineament maps extracted from DEM by GIS to study potential of unsaturated zone and natural basalt caves for groundwater artificial recharge in North-East Jordan. The geoelectrical survey characterized the unsaturated zone in the study area. In highly fractured dense lineaments and lineament intersections parts of the study area, aeromagnetic intensity was low and potential for groundwater recharge was high. Beer-Al-Hamam and Al-Fahda caves were found to be high potential for groundwater. Resistivity survey indicated that, the unsaturated zone had suitable thickness for any artificial recharge scheme and presence of lineaments in the unsaturated zone can controls on a flow system of the area. The high values of resistivity with increasing depth indicated presence of layers of clay-free horizons. This character can help for groundwater artificial recharge (Hani Al-Amoush, 2010).

A hydro-geological model can be developed using GIS, SiTEM SEMDI (software for geophysical data analysis) and GEOSCEN3D (for geological modelling) to map groundwater salinity area. Two geophysical methods may also be applied i.e., Time domain electromagnetic (TDEM) and Continuous Vertical Electrical Sounding (CVES) to study soil salinity variation in sedimentary formation of Barotse sub-basin of Zambia. To map the variation of groundwater soil salinity on regional scale, TDEM can be applied. CVES was used for studying saltwater freshwater distribution on local scale. At the shallow depth (less than 10 metre), saline groundwater was found and brackish water can also be found at the depth of 30 metre (Chongo et al., 2011).

As the method is very complicated and requires several secondary processes like VES, VESR, etc. and software (e.g., SiTEM SEMDI) for analysis, it is not so acceptable to the researchers (Srivastava et al., 2012; Chongo et al., 2011).

3.1.6. Application of geoelectrical method in GIS platform for spatial modelling

Srivastava et al. (2012) were made an examination on groundwater prospect zone utilizing Remote Sensing, GIS and Geoelectrical resistivity on Dhanbad, Jharkhand. The target of their investigation was the investigation, assessment and administration as well as mapping and get ready administration techniques for ground water assets of the examination region. IRS LISS II multi-band remote detecting information alongside the geographical and geophysical resistivity sounding information (i.e., Vertical Electrical Soundings or VES information) has been dissected to finish the procedure. By applying electrical resistivity method, the depth of occurrence of ground water zone and the area of well destinations can be identified more viably. From the study, few decisions can be taken:

Firstly, geographically the groundwater is kept in the secondary porosity i.e. fractured zone, fault, joint and weathered column. Secondly, based on resistivity variation with depth, the estimation of depth and distribution of groundwater can be possible, along with that, the presence of weathered zone can be determined by resistivity value of less

than 51ohm-m which indicates favourable zone for accumulation of groundwater. Thirdly, zones with higher potential are mainly found along the lineaments and in pediment areas whereas geomorphic units like covered pedi plains, peni plains and denundational slopes are direct to great groundwater prospective zones and undulating upland and covered pediments with intermontane valley, mostly kept in undulating upland, are the zones of poor groundwater prospect. Identification of groundwater prospective zone in Jharia and Raniganj coalfields of Dhanbad district in Jharkhand has been conducted by using geoelectrical method. Besides taking help from the remote sensing applications like interpretation to separate hydromorphogeological units and to delineate the major trends of lineaments with the technique of False Colour Composite (FCC) of different bands of Landsat-5 Multi Spectral Scanner (MSS) data, geoelectrical techniques has also been applied. Based on the hydrogeomorphological and hydrogeological studies, geoelectrical resistivity investigations evolved as suitable for the selection of sites for tube.

The resistivity would vary from 120-150 ohm m for water-bearing weathered/fractured rocks and the most promising zone for groundwater exploration was the blue zone, where dug wells may be dug up to depths of 30±5m (Rai et al., 2005).

Identification of groundwater potential zone by using Vertical Electrical Soundings (VES) technique was the method of geoelectrical survey has been applied in Medak

district, Andhra Pradesh. Besides using the VES survey using schlumberger electrode configuration in 26 different locations, different methods for measuring the resistivity values, schlumberger soundings, etc. has also been used. The understanding and preparing of the information has been done subjectively and quantitatively by utilizing partial curve matching technique to acquire the resistivity estimations of various subsurface layers and their comparing thickness. From the elucidation of VES bends, 3 to 5 subsurface layers where recognized inside the investigation range. From the examinations one might say that, in a hard rock condition, Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) has turned out to be exceptionally dependable for underground water considers and in this manner the strategy can incredibly be utilized for shallow and profound underground water geophysical resistivity examination and the investigation can undoubtedly comprehend the water bearing limit of a specific area inside the examination territory (Selvam and Sivasubramanian, 2012).

Besides the requirement of incorporation of VES data, the main limitation of this method is that, it cannot provide information about recharge, groundwater flow, etc. and the existence of comparatively thin layers of terrible hydraulic conductivity which can be of extraordinary significance in hydrological issues. Troubles emerge likewise in the translation of progressive changes of the groundwater with profundity (Van Dam, 1976).

Fig. 1 Flow Diagram of the Methodology (Needhidasan and Nallanathel, 2013)

3.2. Use of MODFLOW in groundwater modelling

MODFLOW (Modular Three-Dimensional Ground-Water Flow Model) is the USGS modular finite-difference flow model that explains the equation of groundwater flow. The groundwater flow from the aquifers can be rebuilt by using this program. The code is open area free programming, composed principally in Fortran, and can order and keep running on platforms like MS Windows or Unix.

It is a numerical model administering fractional differential equation for a restricted aquifer utilized as a part of MODFLOW is:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[K_{xx} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[K_{yy} \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[K_{zz} \frac{\partial h}{\partial z} \right] + W = S_s \frac{\partial h}{\partial t}$$

Where, K_{xx} , K_{yy} and K_{zz} are hydraulic conductivity along the x, y, and z coordinates, i.e., L/T; h indicates potentiometric head (L); W shows a volumetric flux per unit volume representing sources and/or sinks of water, where extractions reflecting negative values and injections reflecting positive values, i.e., T^{-1} ; S_s indicates specific storage of the porous material, i.e., L^{-1} and t is time

MODFLOW code is used to simulate 3D area, steady state flow and transient flow of anisotropic, heterogeneous, layered aquifer. MODFLOW is also applied to show structural transfer along with mass transfer elements of hydrological system and can give essential data for arranging of a powerful subsurface drainage system to anticipate soil salinization. MODFLOW is not applicable for varying density like saltwater intrusion and for perched aquifer (Scibek et al., 2005; Mirlas, 2012).

Among the available software for groundwater modelling, MODFLOW has turned into the overall standard groundwater flow model. It is utilized to imitate systems for supply of water, remediation control and dewatering of mine. At the point of application, MODFLOW is perceived as the standard model. MODFLOW can be described in detail along with the various methods of groundwater modelling to explain whether the model is beneficial or not (Kumar, 1997).

GIS and Visual MODFLOW can be integrated to achieve the satisfactory simulation results. The main intent of such process was to highlight the usage of Visual MODFLOW and GIS techniques to introduce an exhaustive audit on their applications to groundwater hydrology. GIS software ArcView can be used for all the thematic maps which were overlaid and the final overlaid map that showing the ground water potential zones can be obtained. Along with these, collateral data like, rainfall and agricultural data, temperature data, well data, aquifer details, tank details, population data etc. can also be obtained (Needhidasan and Nallanathel, 2013). The implementation of MODFLOW model can be explained by the flow diagram (Fig. 1). GIS can be used as a very effective tool for the data compilation and assessment and visual MODFLOW can be used to simulate water levels in the observation wells to draw the long term water table trend and water table trend for individual wells for pre & post monsoon using 20 years water level data (Needhidasan and Nallanathel, 2013).

The main limitation of this method is that, during implementation of this method the water should have dynamic viscosity and a constant density throughout the

process. Along with that it does not have any evidence of allowing the incorporation of other factors or judgments with existing maps.

3.3. Weightage assignment and geoinformatics-based modelling

Integration of thematic map and modelling in the study of identification of groundwater potential zones in the hilly terrain along with the plain surface can be done properly. The integration of all the reclassified thematic layers should be applied with one another through GIS using the weighting overlay analysis. Before applying the process of weightage overlay, the categorization of all the determining factors like lineament density, drainage density, DEM and slope, LULC and most importantly knowledge-based weight assignment should be completed (Gupta and Srivastava, 2010).

The learning based weight task process was completed for each component utilizing the multi-criteria evaluation (MCE). As the inferred datasets have distinctive degrees of impact on groundwater event, the considered layers of overseeing components can be coordinated and dissected utilizing that system. MCE depended on the analytical hierarchy principle (Saaty, 1980) where a combined correlation network was set up for the deciding criteria (lineament thickness, seepage thickness, incline and LULC). Singular weights and guide scores ought to have been given independently. At last, the aggregate weights of the last incorporated polygons can be determined as total of result of the weights allocated to the diverse layers as indicated by their reasonableness (Gupta and Srivastava, 2010).

Groundwater potential zone can also be detected through integration of various thematic maps that describing favourable groundwater zones into a single groundwater potential map with the help of GIS. The best result can be found through the processes of spatial database building was the spatial data analysis and data integration. In the final stage of data integration, integration of all the data should be accumulated from thematic maps like geology, geomorphology, drainage density, lineament and slope with appropriate factors. Based on weightage assignment, various thematic maps can be reclassified and integrated to Spatial Analyst tool using the "Raster Calculator" function. Many researchers have assigned weightage for different layers depending on the similar type of work (Srinivasa and Jugran, 2003, Krishnamurthy et al., 1996; Saraf and Choudhary, 1998). For integration of various thematic maps, a simple arithmetical model can be adopted by averaging the weightage and finally, from groundwater potential point of view, the final map can be prepared and categorized into five zones such as Very good, Good, Moderate to good, Moderate and Poor (Prasad et al., 2007).

Almost every researcher worked in this domain has followed more or less same process to get the proper result of assessments or findings for groundwater potential zone using GIS. Likewise, Nagarajan and Singh, 2009 has made a study on assessment of groundwater potential zone in Kattakulathur block of Tamil Nadu. According to the study, by overlaying all the thematic maps in terms of weighted overlay methods, groundwater potential zones can be obtained using the spatial analysis tool in ArcGIS 9.2. Respective ranking may also be given for each individual

parameter of each thematic map and weights were assigned during the process of weighted overlay analysis. In accordance with the influence, the weightage has been given such as soil 25%, geomorphology 25%, land use/land cover 25%, slope 15%, lineament 5% and drainage/streams 5% and found the potential zones in terms of good, moderate and poor zones with the respective areas.

Integration of all the data of thematic maps of geomorphology and geology, soil type, land slope, drainage density, recharge pattern and surface water body can be done for getting the appropriate result about groundwater potential zone. The checking of those spatial maps may operate with respect to other database layers by the overlaying technique. Assignment of the suitable weights to the themes and their individual features after understanding their hydrogeological importance can properly explain the cause of groundwater occurrence in the study area. Deriving the normalized weights of the individual themes and their different features by the help of Saaty's analytical hierarchy process (AHP) was extremely normal in such sort of studies. In the wake of determining the ordinary weights of all the topical layers and each component under individual subjects, the mix of all the topical layers with each other utilizing MapInfo GIS programming was especially solid so as to delineate groundwater potential zones in the study area. To conclude that, with the help of pair-wise comparison matrix the groundwater potential map of the study area can be divided into three distinct classes (zones) represented as 'good', 'moderate' and 'poor' groundwater potential zone in the study area (Hutti and Nijagunappa, 2011).

Weighted Index Overlay Analysis (WIOA) or Weighted Overlay Analysis (WOA) is a basic and viable method for consolidating and examination of multi-class maps (Nag, 2005). The quality of this technique in view of the way that human judgment/master conclusion including past writing can be joined into the examination through a weighting framework. WOA method thinks about the relative significance of the parameters and the classes having a place with every parameter by weighting. As there is no standard scale for WOA, criteria should be characterized and every parameter appointed by its relative significance (Gumma et al., 2013; Nag, 2005; Saraf and Chowdhury, 1998).

4. Conclusion

The rate of groundwater usage is increasing day by day for both irrigation and domestic purposes. Besides, the unplanned and limitless groundwater extraction, the climate change is also significant cause for lowering the groundwater recent years. Therefore, a detailed investigation will always be helpful in the study of the efficient and sustainable management of this scarce natural resource. Identifying the ground water potential zones using geo spatial techniques which include remote sensing, GIS and AHP techniques were found to be efficient to minimize time and money. Satellite imageries, SOI topographic maps and conventional data are required to prepare the thematic layers like drainage density, groundwater level, geomorphology, soil, landuse and land cover, geology, rainfall and temperature, slope, aspect, and lineament density. By assigning proper weightage to the various thematic through AHP technique and integration in the GIS environment, the groundwater potential zone map can

be easily prepared. The present study can be used for better interpretation and to plan a research work on groundwater potential zone, water resources management and future artificial recharge projects by the applications of Remote Sensing and GIS.

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